

ISic2912

I.Sicily inscription 2912

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Piazza Armerina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Piazza Armerina, in store

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645302

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1982. Die Villa von Piazza Armerina, Residenz des kaiserlichen Prokurators, und ein mit ihr verbundenes Emporium von Henna. In Papenfuss, D., Strocka, V.M.(eds.), *Palast und Hütte : Beiträge zum Bauen und Wohnen im Altertum von Archäologen, Vor- und Frühgeschichtlern: Tagungsbeiträge eines Symposiums der Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung, Bonn-Bad Godesberg, veranstaltet vom 25.-30. November 1979 in Berlin*. Mainz. pp. 493-513. At 502 no.7 fig.10

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Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 47 n.234

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